

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2017-18 academic year for MPT

BASIC LIFE SUPPORT (BLS)

**COLLEGE OF
PHYSIOTHERAPY**

**COURSE DURATION: 40
Hours**

This course aims to make students be able to recognize life-threatening emergencies, give high-quality chest compressions, deliver appropriate ventilations and provide early use of an AED. Students will work on to complete BLS skills practice and skills testing. Course includes didactic lessons and simulated clinical scenarios.

Venue
City campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

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Course period	From September 2017 till November 2017, during 1 st semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	MPT 1 st year postgraduates (2017 batch)

Course Outcomes:

At the end of the course candidate will be able to-

1. Define the basic steps of CPR; use of AED and steps to relieve choking.
2. Explain the importance of early CPR and early defibrillation.
3. Analyse the importance of each link in the adult and paediatric Chain of Survival.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MODULE	TOPIC	HOURS
1	General Concepts: Introduction, High – Quality CPR, The Chain of Survival, indications for CPR. Team Dynamics: Roles During a Resuscitation Attempt	4
2	BLS for Adults: BLS General Concepts, BLS Healthcare Provider Adult Cardiac Arrest Algorithm, Adult 1 – Rescuer BLS Sequence, Adult chest compressions, Adult breaths, Adult 2 - Rescuer BLS Sequence. BLS for Infants and Children: BLS General Concepts, BLS Healthcare, Provider Paediatric Cardiac Arrest Algorithm for the Single Rescuer, Infant and child 1-Rescuer BLS Sequence, Infant and child chest compressions, Infant and child breaths, Infant 2 - Rescuer BLS Sequence.	10
3	Automated External Defibrillator (AED): For Adult And Children 8 Years Of Age And Older: Using the AED, special Circumstances. Automated External Defibrillator for Infants and Children Less Than 8 years of Age: Using the AED, special Circumstances.	8
4	Ventilation Technique: CPR and Breaths with an Advanced Airway, Rescue Breathing, Techniques for Giving Breaths Without a Barrier Device; Opioid – Associated life threatening emergencies.	8

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. Basic Life support by AHA Association, 2015 guidelines.
2. First Aid for children Fast by Cameron M.
3. First Aid by Parulekar SV.
4. First Aid Emergencies Yeshuai.
5. First Aid manual by St. Andrews Association.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Certificate of Completion

presented to

NAZIR AHMED

for attending and completing the value added course on "Basic Life Support (BLS)"
conducted from September to November 2017

Total Hours - 40

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'N. Mageswaran'.

Dr. N. Mageswaran (PT)
Associate Professor
Course Instructor

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. Rajasekar (PT)
Dean
College of Physiotherapy